

To Develop the Orange Rind Powder for Identification of Latent Fingerprint

AYUSH KUMAR¹

M.sc Forensic Science

(Vivekananda Global University Jaipur Rajasthan)

Abstract:- Many Types of powder available in the market to identify the latent fingerprint some powders are toxic in our body to affect the body organ. I have attempt to use new powder for develop the latent fingerprint which are simple, non-toxic, less expensive than the commercially used fingerprint powder. These are easily available in every fruit shops. This type of work has not been reported previously and can provide the information to the investigators in cases of scarcity or non-availability of regular conventional fingerprint development powders. This is use simple and novice in the field in the Forensic fingerprint can also do it.

Keywords:- Latent fingerprint, Orange rind, Toxic, Non-toxic, Investigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fingerprint impression are made by papillary gland ridges on the ends of the finger and thumb, fingerprints are not same every person fingerprint are unique every person in the world, Fingerprints are present in every crime scene types of physical evidence to identify the criminal three types of fingerprint found in crime scene latent, patent and plastic fingerprint. Latent fingerprints are not visual in naked eye latent finger print thus require the powder method for visualization of fingerprint. This powder identify the fingerprint very easily this powder is non-toxic because do not use any chemical substances in this powder, it is natural, simple and less expensive powder. Fingerprint present in crime scene in cases of murder, theft, rape, etc.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

➤ Material

Orange Rind, Match box, Grinder

➤ Method

Take the Orange Rind than dry the orange rind in sunshine for two days. After two days than orange rind burn in fire than orange rind ash is collected than grind the ash in Grinder than develop the Orange rind powder to identify the latent fingerprint.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To easily identify the fingerprint to new develop orange rind powder, Fingerprints are seen in paint wall, Glass, paper, wood table etc.

Fig 1:- Orange rind powder

IV. CONCLUSION

This powder could be successfully used in nature in developing latent fingerprint or different types of surfaces in the future this powder non-toxic and simple in nature, this powder is not harmful in our body and less expensive powder.

Fig 2:- (Plastic surface)

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Fig 3:- (Paint wall surface)

Fig 4:- (Paper surface)

Fig 5:- (Wood surface)

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